

Comparative Evaluation of the Effects of Amlodipine, Cilnidipine, and Calcium Channel Antagonists on the QT Interval in Hypertensive PatientsSumita Katiyar¹, C. M. Kamaal², Modh Anjoom³, Priya Choudhary⁴¹Junior Resident-3, Department of Pharmacology, S.M.M.H. Government Medical College, Saharanpur, U.P.²Professor, Department of Pharmacology, S.M.M.H. Government Medical College, Saharanpur, U.P.³Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacology, S.M.M.H. Government Medical College, Saharanpur, U.P.⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacology, S.M.M.H. Government Medical College, Saharanpur, U.P.

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Abstract:

Background: 12-lead electrocardiography measures the length of the QT interval, which is a marker of myocardial repolarization and is frequently used to characterize cardiac abnormalities, identify cardiac toxicity, and assess drug safety. After controlling for the impact of other risk variables, the QT interval in hypertension can predict the risk of both coronary events and cardiovascular death. Calcium channel blockers are the first-line medication for treating hypertension, according to the American Heart Association and JNC VIII. Numerous investigations have shown that amlodipine and cilnidipine, when taken at comparable doses, have an equipotent antihypertensive impact. Aims of this study to compare and evaluate the effects of calcium channel antagonists amlodipine and cilnidipine on QT interval among hypertensive patients.

Methods: During that time, 129 patients in all were screened, evaluated, and recruited as study participants. Following enrollment, the patients were split into one category: hypertensive patients (n = 80). Amlodipine (2.5–10 mg) or cilnidipine (5–20 mg) with or without an angiotensin receptor blocker (ARB) was administered to a subset of patients, and (2) hypertensive patients with managed diabetes (n = 49) Selected participants were given antidiabetic medicine combined with either amlodipine (2.5–10 mg) or cilnidipine (5–20 mg), with or without an ARB. QT interval/ $\sqrt{\text{RR}}$ (relative risk [RR] interval), where RR interval = 60/heart rate, is calculated using Bazett's method (the most often used), with normal QTc ≤ 440 ms. Patients with hypertension had their QT intervals tested both at baseline and after a year of medication.

Results: Although there was no therapeutic significance, there was a very significant decrease in QTc with cilnidipine therapy and a significant increase with amlodipine medication. Extremely significant and clinically important differences between amlodipine and cilnidipine were observed while comparing their effects.

Conclusion: According to this study, cilnidipine is a better option than amlodipine for patients with a lengthy QT interval since it shortens the QTc interval.

Keywords: Hypertension, Amlodipine, Cilnidipine, QT Interval.

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Introduction

About 20% of people worldwide suffer with systemic hypertension, one of the most prevalent non-communicable diseases in human history.[1] The disease affects all segments of the Indian population, with urban areas having a higher prevalence (30.9%) than rural areas (21.2%). Regular blood pressure monitoring contributes to early diagnosis of hypertension, even though the majority of people with early hypertension do not exhibit any symptoms.[2] Calcium channel blockers are among the first-line medications for uncomplicated hypertension, according to the 2007 American Heart Association guidelines.[3]

Calcium channel blockers are the first line of treatment for both the general Black community and non-Black people, including those with diabetes, according to JNC VIII guidelines. 12-lead electrocardiography measures the length of the QT interval, which is a marker of myocardial repolarization and is frequently used to characterize cardiac abnormalities, identify cardiac toxicity, and assess drug safety. After controlling for the impact of other risk variables, the QT interval in hypertension can predict the risk of both coronary events and cardiovascular death. QT interval prolongation is caused by a complex mechanism

that includes increased left ventricular mass (LVM) and cardiomyocyte hypertrophy, along with changes in the transmural dispersion of repolarization in the left ventricle, changes in the tone of the autonomic nervous system in certain hypertensive patients, and mechano-electrical feedback, though the latter is less likely. While reducing blood pressure (BP) is the main objective of antihypertensive medication therapy, and different people have varying preferences for antihypertensive medication regimens, the effects of various antihypertensives on the QTc interval differ. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to assess and contrast the effects of amlodipine and cilnidipine, the two most widely used CCBs, on hypertension individuals' QT intervals.

Material and Methods

This observational study was carried out over a 24-month period at the medicine outpatient department at S.M.M.H Government Medical College, Saharanpur, and U.P. and is comparative, non-blinded, single-centered, prospective, and parallel groups. Every patient taking part in the trial gave their written informed permission. Patients with hypertension were chosen for the study based on inclusion and exclusion criteria.

All selected male and female patients age more than 40 years & less than 60 years; body mass index (BMI) >18.5 to <30 kg/m² (normal and pre-obese), essential hypertension of mild-to-moderate cases (Stage I and Stage II) according to JNC 7 (those systolic BP (SBP) <180 and diastolic BP (DBP) <110), phase of microalbuminuria spot urinary albumin-creatinine ratio (ACR), ACR <300 mg/g, hypertensive patients on amlodipine (2.5–10 mg) and cilnidipine (5–20 mg) or combination with angiotensin receptor blocker (ARB) (in a dose equivalent to 40 mg of telmisartan) and controlled diabetic patient (hemoglobin A1c [HBA1c] ≤7) were included in this study. Patients with age less than 40 years and more than 60 years, BMI <18.5 to

>29.99 kg/sq. mt, hypertension with SBP ≥180 and DBP ≥110, secondary hypertension or taking anti-hypertensive medicine other than additional ACEI/ARB, uncontrolled diabetes (HBA1c >7), serum creatinine ≥1.2, liver disease, ACR >300 mg/gm (spot urine), pioglitazone, heart failure, heart block, and aortic stenosis, NSAID for long-term; corticosteroid and sex steroids, any other chronic illness (rheumatoid arthritis, tuberculosis, and protein-energy malnutrition) and alcoholic (consume more than moderate amount), hypothyroid, and varicose vein were excluded in this study.

During that time, 129 patients in all had screening, examinations, and were chosen to participate in the study. They received signed informed permission after being briefed about the study in the local language. Following enrollment, the patients were split into one category: hypertensive patients (n = 80). (2) Hypertensive patients with managed diabetes (n = 49) were given either amlodipine (2.5–10 mg) or cilnidipine (5–20 mg) with or without an ARB. Selected participants were given antidiabetic medicine combined with either amlodipine (2.5–10 mg) or cilnidipine (5–20 mg), with or without an ARB. The baseline and 12-month QT intervals were measured. The corrected QT interval is QTc. QT interval/√ (relative risk [RR] interval), where RR Interval = 60/heart rate (HR), is calculated using Bazett's method (the most often used), with a normal QTc of ≤440 ms. The patient is more susceptible to torsade de pointes if their QTc is prolonged.

Results

QTc (corrected QT interval) analysis is presented in Table 1 for hypertensive (non-diabetic and diabetic) individuals comparing amlodipine and cilnidipine medication. A comparison of the changes in QTc following a 12-month course of amlodipine and cilnidipine medication is presented in Table 2. This figure illustrates how amlodipine raised QTc while cilnidipine decreased it.

Table 1: Analysis of QTc (corrected QT interval), on comparison between amlodipine and cilnidipine treatment, on hypertensive (non-diabetic and diabetic) patients

Data Analyzed at mean±SD	Hypertensive patients n=80			Hypertensive diabetic patients n=49		
	Amlodipine n=41	Cilnidipine n=39	P (95% CI)	Amlodipine n=23	Cilnidipine n=26	P (95% CI)
Base line	400.53±18.96	398.15±18.7	0.4273 NS	395.77±18.37	393.31±16.61	0.4861 NS
12 months**	403.32*±17.93	389.38 [‡] ±17.89	0.0001 (8.32<13.94 <19.55)	398.04*±19.21	384.13 [‡] ±13.94	0.0001 (7.26<13.91 <20.56)
P(95% CI)	0.0001 (1.47<2.79 <4.11)	0.0001 (-10<-8.77 <-7.45)		0.0409 (-0.10<2.28 <4.45)	0.0001 (-10.58<-9.17 <-7.76)	

Table 2: Comparative analysis of change in QTc with amlodipine and cilnidipine treatment after 12 months. This figure depicts that amlodipine caused increase in QTc and cilnidipine caused decrease in QTc

Data Analyzed at mean±SD	Hypertensive patients n=80	
	Amlodipine (n=41)	Cilnidipine (n=39)
Base line	400.53±18.96	398.15±18.7
12 months	403.32*±17.93	389.38 [‡] ±17.89

A comparison of the changes in QTc following a 12-month course of amlodipine and cilnidipine medication is presented in Table 3. This Table illustrates how amlodipine raised QTc while cilnidipine decreased it.

Table 3: Comparative analysis of change in QTc with amlodipine and cilnidipine treatment after 12 months. This figure depicts that amlodipine caused increase in QTc and cilnidipine caused decrease in QTc

Data Analyzed at mean±SD	Hypertensive diabetic patients n=49	
	Amlodipine (n=23)	Cilnidipine (n=26)
Base line	395.77±18.37	393.31±16.61
12 months	398.04*±19.21	384.13 [‡] ±13.94

Discussion

According to Mozos and Serban, LVH and hypertension are linked to a higher incidence of extended QT intervals. In [4] "Although hypertrophy can normalize wall tension, it is a risk factor for QT-prolongation and cardiac sudden death," observed Kang as well. In [5] According to Klimas et al., "a progressive increase in the duration of the QT interval is linked to the development of cardiac hypertrophy and hypertension, and it is not directly related to the increased left ventricular weight that has been observed in spontaneously diabetic rats." [6]

Elevated repolarization ability is directly linked to sympathetic cardiac activity in patients with essential hypertension, according to research by Baumert et al. [7] The ventricular myocardium of healthy persons is directly impacted by autonomic circumstances, leading to variations in QT that are not dependent on HR, according to Magnano et al. In [8] According to Darbar et al., a low-salt diet that activates the sympathetic nervous system makes people more susceptible to drug-induced QT prolongation. [9]

The majority of people with long QT syndrome (LQTS), though not all of them, are known to have cardiac events during periods of heightened sympathetic activation that are brought on by or imitated by medications, physical activity, stress, or emotion. The possible application of left cardiac sympathectomy in the management of LQTS patients contributes to the ANS's involvement in this condition. [10-12]

The effect of antihypertensive medications on the length of the QT interval varies, according to Klimas et al. The processes that underlie their impact are dependent on (a) modifications in LVM, (b) autonomic nervous system tone, and (c) alterations in cardiac ion channel activity. The data about the different effects of antihypertensive drugs on

the length of the QT interval should be taken into account when implementing long-term pharmacotherapy for hypertension, even though the main objective of antihypertensive drug therapy is lowering blood pressure and different people have different preferences when it comes to antihypertensive drug treatment regimens. In line with our research, Porthan et al. demonstrated that "amlodipine seems to have no repolarization effects." Milovanović et al.'s study [13] revealed that amlodipine decreases the QTc interval (426.94 ± 25.3 vs. 424.08 ± 33.7 ms) without statistical significance, while [14] the current study shows that amlodipine increases the QTc, 400.53 ± 18.96 vs. 403.32 ± 17.93 in DM(-); 395.77 ± 18.37 vs. 398.04 ± 19.21 in DM(+) patients.

The multifactorial mechanism of QT interval prolongation involves increased LVM and cardiomyocyte hypertrophy, along with alterations in the left ventricular transmural dispersion of repolarization, autonomic nervous system tone in certain hypertensive patients, and mechano-electrical feedback, though the latter is less likely. A few investigations have already shown that LVH causes delayed ventricular conduction, longer and irregular ventricular repolarization, and longer action potential duration. [19–21] The increased thickness of the left ventricle wall and intramural fibrosis, which distorts and prolongs transmural impulse propagation, may be the cause of the prolonged QT interval. It may also be the result of downregulating multiple potassium currents that are involved in repolarization or intraventricular or interventricular conduction delay or block. [22, 23]

Using the heart of canine chronic atrioventricular block model, Takahara et al.'s study found that the QT interval and monophasic action potential durations were decreased exclusively in the cilnidipine group, but not in the amlodipine group [24]. Ventricular electrical remodelling in the

cardiac sudden death model is known to resemble the pathophysiology of LQTS.

The present study clearly studied the effect of cilnidipine on QTc depression, which is greater than that of amlodipine. The exact cellular mechanism or mechanisms by which cilnidipine shortens the ventricular repolarization are still unknown. Angiotensin II reduces cardiac myocytes' IKr, transient outward K⁺ currents (I_{to}), and inward rectifier K⁺ currents (IK1), while aldosterone reduces I_{to}, according to earlier in vitro electrophysiological research [25–27].

Conclusion

Cilnidipine is a better option than amlodipine for patients with a lengthy QT interval since it shortens the QTc interval, according to this study.

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